

THE ROLE AND SIGNIFICANCE OF POETRY IN JADID
LITERATURE

Abdilakimov Dilruxjon

The main doctoral student of the Department of Uzbek Literature of the
National University of Uzbekistan.

adilruxjon@gmail.com

Abstract: National independence motifs are analyzed in the poetry of Fitrat and Cholpon, representatives of modern literature, and the contribution of their work to the development of modern Uzbek literature is studied.

Key words and phrases: Jadid, Jadid literature, classic literature, new Uzbek literature, Naim Karimov, Fitrat, Chulpan

Throughout the history of mankind, people have been striving for beauty, art, and literature. Especially literary works have always fascinated people. Because only the art of words introduces people to feelings that they have not yet experienced, how a person should be and how to behave in situations that he has not experienced. Each work of art is a world within itself, and the reader lives with the heroes of the work he is reading, when he cries, he cries, and when he is happy, he is even happier. Literature is sometimes referred to as a "treasure of manners". In fact, there is no clear program for raising a perfect person, then the earth would have already turned into a paradise, there would be no wars, thefts, fights, and all the bad things. But a person who has read a work of art and is familiar with literature has a wider understanding of the world and man. It is for this reason that in the history of any nation in the most difficult situations, we witness that selfless people who understood its pain and felt sorry for it either read many works or wrote such works themselves.

Vol. 2. Issue 3

At the beginning of the 20th century, the Uzbek people were colonized and far behind in development. Religious zealots became a big obstacle in the way of science. The people were unjustly kept away from knowledge and development by the occupying power. In such a difficult situation, the most dedicated children of the nation, who were called Jadids, entered the social, political and literary field. They understood the atmosphere of that time very well. Seeing that the efforts made with weapons to achieve independence (Polat Khan and Dukchi Eshon events) did not work, the Jadids considered that the most important tool in this way is to wake up the people from the sleep of heedlessness, to bring them in line with the times, and to make them aware of their rights. “To make Turkestan literate and enlightened, to turn it into a rich and prosperous, free and prosperous homeland, first of all, to achieve independence, to get rid of the yoke of colonialism was the main goal and task of the revolutionary movement”¹ was press and literature. Jadids paid great attention to literature. Mumtaz broke the traditional patterns and renewed both prose and poetry, formed a new school of dramaturgy and translation. With these services, Jadids started a new Uzbek literature and took a worthy place in this literature.

Poetry has been leading in the history of Uzbek literature for many years. Aruz is the absolute leader in the poetry of our classical literature. Turkic peoples, like Arabs and Persians, have been creating their best examples of works in Aruz during their several thousand years of history. This process continued until the beginning of the 20th century. At the same time, in the territory of Turkestan, representatives of the movement called Jadidism started to update literature as well as other fields. As a result, the old stereotyped poetry was enriched with new genres, and the traditional aruz weight was changed. Poetry and literature in general came closer to the people, penetrated among them. For nothing Fitrat did

¹ B.Qosimov. Jadidchilik, - Milliy uyg'onish va o'zbek filologiyasi masalalari. – T. 1993, 21-22 betlar

not say that the weight of a finger is our national weight². The leading field of Jadid literature is poetry. Jadid poetry, which was sharply different from Uzbek classical poetry in terms of weight, language, style, and ideology, laid the foundation stone for the development of Uzbek literature in a new direction in the 20th century. The fact that the Uzbek people lived in an environment of ignorance and ignorance at the beginning of the century, indifference to changes in the fields of social life, science, culture and technology, being stuck in the vortex of everyday household problems and falling into a morally helpless situation is not only a matter of modern journalism, but also of poetry. determined the ideological direction. Jadids tried to hold up a mirror to the people's people with their poems, to reflect their strange and poor life, soulless state and pessimistic mood in this mirror.

When we talk about Jadid's poetry, the figure of Cholpan comes to mind first of all. Naim Karimovdi is one of the biggest researchers of Cholpon's work. Naim Karimov's thoughts on the lyrics of Cholpon are close to the views of Azod Sharafiddinov. Analyzing the Poet's poem "Qizil bayroq", the author does not go far from the general thoughts expressed in this poem. Because the title of this poem also reminds of the Soviet flag, many critics believe that the Soviets were sung in this poem, and that Cholpan looked at it with great hope in the early years of the revolution. Naim Karimov sums up his thoughts and says: "This serves as the main evidence in covering the topic of Cholpon and October."³ But some of these views changed a little after the scientist's career⁴. In February 1917, in his poem "Uzbek yoshlarina", which was published in "Nazokat" newspaper, Cholpon was pleased with the event and called on his young compatriots to serve in the interests of the

² Фитрат А. Аруз хақида / Танланган асарлар. Ж.В. – Тошкент: Маънавият, 2010. – Б. 227 бет

³ Каримов Н. Абдулхамид Сулаймон ўғли Чўлпон. – Тошкент: Фан, 1991. – Б. 43

⁴ Look: Каримов Н. Чўлпон. – Тошкент: Шарқ, 2003

people, and considered this to be an honorable task: You work for the nation. This is a blessing to you,

It is not a pleasure to work tirelessly for the nation...

Yes, the critic was right when he made these points. Cholpon really welcomed this historic event with great joy. All intellectuals of this period looked at this event with great hope. The hope that this event will bring freedom and liberty to the Uzbek people has hindered their realistic view of reality. But the bloodbath of the autonomy of Turkestan proved that it was all just an illusion. The destruction that began in the country made the poet take a pen in his hand:

Your blue-blue, beautiful meadows are pressed,

There is neither herd nor yearling on them.

On which gallows are the herdsman hanged?

Instead of horse riding and sheep riding.

Oh, cry, why is that?

It can be observed that many cholponologists analyzed the poem “Buzulgan Olkaga” from different points of view. But in almost all of these views, we can see that the analysis of this poem in connection with the social and political life of that time is clearly manifested. Naim Karimov also evaluates from this point of view: “In this poem, he described the horrors that happened in the country with great courage”⁵. The critic's assessment of the courage to write and publish a poem on such a topic at that time means that it is connected with social and political life. More than one use of adjectives in relation to the meadow also served to increase the effectiveness of the poem. “Why is that?” the lyrical hero knows all this, but the reasons cannot be clearly stated. That is why the poet addressed the reader with a question and was able to shake hearts. Analyzing the poem "Men and Others", its theme You work for the nation. This is a blessing to you,

⁵ Karimov N. Abdulhamid Sulaymon o'g'li Cho'lpon.-T.: Fan, 1991. B.46

It is not a pleasure to work tirelessly for the nation...

Yes, the critic was right when he made these points. Cholpon really welcomed this historic event with great joy. All intellectuals of this period looked at this event with great hope. The hope that this event will bring freedom and liberty to the Uzbek people has hindered their realistic view of reality. But the bloodbath of the autonomy of Turkestan proved that it was all just an illusion. The destruction that began in the country made the poet take a pen in his hand:

Your blue-blue, beautiful meadows are pressed,
There is neither herd nor yearling on them.
On which gallows are the herdsman hanged?
Instead of horse riding and sheep riding.
Oh, cry, why is that?

It can be observed that many cholponologists analyzed the poem "Buzulgan Olkaga" from different points of view. But in almost all of these views, we can see that the analysis of this poem in connection with the social and political life of that time is clearly manifested. Naim Karimov also evaluates from this point of view: "In this poem, he described the horrors that happened in the country with great courage." The critic's assessment of the courage to write and publish a poem on such a topic at that time means that it is connected with social and political life. More than one use of adjectives in relation to the meadow also served to increase the effectiveness of the poem. "Why is that?" the lyrical hero knows all this, but the reasons cannot be clearly stated. That is why the poet addressed the reader with a question and was able to shake hearts. Analyzing the poem "I and Others", its theme says that it is still relevant today. The main focus is on the topic. The lyrical hero of the poem is an Uzbek girl. The pitiful fate of Uzbek girls has been revealed very impressively through I and others. Munaqqidin: "Until recently, our literature reflected not today's life, but tomorrow's life that will be built in its place. In this way, he seemed to inspire the reader to new works. In practice, he deceived the

Vol. 2. Issue 3

reader. Cholpon followed the belief that today's wounds should be treated, not hidden. Therefore, it is natural that the truth described in his works seems terrible to the reader who is used to the literature of socialist realism", his words serve to prove our point. Today's reality also scared Cholpon. But he believed in tomorrow, tomorrow will be better. Next, the poem "Khalq", which is one of the best examples of Cholpan's work and caused the most objections in its time, will be analyzed. In the poem, it is not critical romanticism that the poet expresses such thoughts about the people who are silently enduring such oppression, injustice and scorn, but it is true that it is related to the hidden potential of the people, the embers of struggle that are unknowingly burned in their blood. able to evaluate. It is no exaggeration to say that Cholpon's skill in using words is fully demonstrated in the poem. The rhythmic repetition of the folk word serves to increase musicality and effectiveness. In a certain sense, this poem was a warning bell to the colonialists. The last two verses show that the lyrical hero is the poet himself: "Let's take all the power from the people, open our arms and go into the people." "Cholpan saw the power hidden in the people's bosom with his perceptive eyes in this way. At the same time, he felt the need to receive support from the people and to be their leader." Summing up the poet's work: "Cholpon was a master of Uzbek poetry, rich in delicate and elegant sounds, singing the flowers of life that blossomed over beautiful and transparent feelings. But the era required him to bring the sounds of shackles and rifles into Uzbek poetry, to express the open and hidden struggle behind these shackles". As a student, Abdurauf Fitrat wrote poems "worthy of being a devan" (Sadriiddin Ainiy). At first, he gives his poems the pseudonym "Mijmar" ("a vessel (mangal) in which various aromatic things such as musk-anbar are put on fire"). According to the writings of Sadriiddin Aini: "Although he wrote ghazals and odes even before the period of Intiboh (awakening

from ignorance), they did not have the polish, burning and burning of today's poems.”⁶

Fitrat, known as Jadid, struck fear into the heart of the existing system with his ideas in his works. That is why Said Olim Khan does not allow his poems to be published in Bukhara. That's why the poet's collection "Sayha" (invocation, call, call) was published in Istanbul in 1329 A.H., melody in 1911 at the student poet's own expense. Phyratologist scientist Hamidulla Boltaboyev notes that this collection is now stored in the Istanbul Dorilfununi Library, and its cover is marked with the inscription "Fitrat. Sayha. "National Poems" was written in Persian and printed in the Arabic alphabet. More than ten poems selected from it were published in the July 1914 issue of "Sadoyi Turkistan" newspaper. In the collection, after each stanza of these poems, its content is explained in Turkish⁷.

Example:

Bozam, the poem is buried in the air,
Par mizanad dilam, yagzoyi goreston.

Content: I felt like crying,
My heart is crying in the sky.

Fitrat was a talented poet. He started his work by writing poetry. His poems were about the Motherland. The poet felt, saw and knew the troubles that befell his country. He was well aware that his only claim was to wake up his compatriots from the sleep of heedlessness and turn on the lights of spirituality. The poet, well aware of the great role of literature, words, especially poetry, did everything he could, created and wrote poems. Political persecution, various censorship, and threats could not stop him from this path. In his poems, the poet said, "The pain of the homeland is endless, and its injuries are fatal. He shouted his love to her. He

⁶ Karimov N. Abdulhamid Sulaymon o'g'li Cho'lpon.-T.: Fan, 1991. B. 49

⁷ H.Boltaboyev. Fitrat va jadidchilik – T.: O'zbekiston. 2007. B. -71

was proud of him. He kept it holy from everything. He knew it as "Qiblagoh", "Sajdagoh", and called it "Izzi Sharafi"⁸.

The works of Fitrat and Cholpon, the greatest representatives of modern literature and the founders of new Uzbek poetry, were full of patriotic ideas and the dream of independence. In a difficult socio-political situation, they were able to express their dreams in various artistic ways.

References:

1. N.Karimov, Cho'lpon. – T.: Sharq, 2004. B.276.
Karimov N. Abdulhamid Sulaymon o'g'li Cho'lpon.-T.: Fan, 1991. B. 47
2. Navoiy asarlari lug'ati. Tuzuvchilar: P.Shamsiyev va S.Ibrohimova. – T.: G'.G'ulom nomidagi Adabiyot va san'at nashriyoti, 1973. – B.348.
3. H.Boltaboyev. Fitrat va jadidchilik – T.: O'zbekiston. 2007. B. -71
4. Begali Qosimov. Milliy uyg'onish. – T.: "Ma'naviyat". 2002. B. -368
5. Фитрат А. Аруз хақида / Танланган асарлар. Ж.V. – Тошкент: Маънавият, 2010. – Б. 227 bet

⁸ Begali Qosimov. Milliy uyg'onish. – T.: "Ma'naviyat". 2002. B. -368

